

Investigations on the Adsorptive Property of Silica Gel. Part II. Adsorptive Properties of Silica Gel containing Residual Hydrogen Chloride.

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Whether residual water is essential for the adsorptive properties exhibited by silica gel is a question that has been investigated by several workers. Patrick and others found that the gel deprived of its water by intense heating suffered considerable loss in its adsorptive properties (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, **31**, 1511 ; 1932, **36**, 475). Rao and Doss (*ibid.*, 1931, **35**, 3487) attempted to prepare gel in which water had been replaced by alcohol but found that such displacement was not complete. In the course of an investigation (Part I, p. 322) on the hydrolysis of carbon tetrachloride by activated silica gel, it was noticed that at the end of the reaction the gel was free from water but held with great firmness about 10% of hydrogen chloride by weight. A study of the properties of this gel was undertaken as being of some importance. The adsorptive capacity of the gel for carbon tetrachloride and its selective adsorption from a mixture of alcohol and benzene were measured.

EXPERIMENTAL.

All glass circulation pump.

Silica gel in which water had been replaced by HCl, was prepared by the hydrolysis of carbon tetrachloride as described in the previous Part (p. 322). The gel had about 10 % residual HCl. The adsorption was carried out in a closed system using a modification of the circulation pump (Fig. 1) described by B. S. Rao. (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, **35**, 615). In the modified pump the pulsation of mercury column was produced by movement of a metallic piston-reservoir. The pulsations were communicated to the reservoirs P_1 and P_2 by attaching them with a rubber tubing to the metallic reservoirs of the pump. This modification led to a greater convenience in working. Another improvement consisted in the use of mercury valves made out of filter tubes of pyrex, specially prepared in this laboratory. The entire circulation pump was made of pyrex glass. Interchangeable ground glass joints, having accurately ground convex and concave surface (listed in Galienkamp and Co.) were employed for connecting the pump with the bubbler L, and the gel tube, G. The spiral S, served as a spring and enabled safe connection between G and L.

Preparation of pyrex filter tubes.—Bruce and Bent (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **53**, 990) suggested the preparation of pyrex filter tubes the method of which was rather laborious. The following modification was found to be very convenient and highly satisfactory. A pyrex glass tube (Fig. 1 a) was slipped on to a nickel disc D, which was rivetted to an iron rod, N; the latter being supported by a nickel plate E. Pyrex glass powder which had been properly sieved, was moistened and placed on the disc D and carefully pressed. The nickel plate with the glass tube was carefully transferred to an electric furnace. The current was then switched on and the furnace heated to bright redness and the tube was allowed to cool in the furnace. When this procedure was employed it was found unnecessary to have any further sealing of the filter disc to the glass tube.

The circulation pump was fitted up in a large air thermostat, constructed on the lines suggested by Vernon (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1931, **27**, 241). A slight modification was effected in the thermo-regulator as shown in the Fig. 1 b. The level of mercury in the regulator could be adjusted by opening the stop-cock S and introducing a glass rod into A, so that at the proper temperature, the mercury in the capillary, just made contact with the electrode P. The stop-cock was then closed. The bulb B was filled with hydrogen so that any sparking at P, caused not fouling of mercury. The following samples of the gel were used for the adsorption of carbon tetrachloride.

TABLE I.

Gel No.	Method of activation.	H ₂ (by wt.)	HCl (by wt.)	Adsorption of CCl ₄ (by wt.)
1.	Dry air passed over the gel at 300° for 5 hr.	2.73%	...	49.63%
2.	Dry nitrogen passed over the gel for 30 hr. at 300°.	2.45	...	49.27
3.	Dry nitrogen passed over the gel for 30 hours at 400°.	1.70	...	43.51
4.	Dry nitrogen saturated with CCl ₄ passed for 30 hrs. at 300°.	9.05	11.08%	43.73
5.	Do. for 30 hrs. at 400°	0.03	8.76	43.2

The carbon tetrachloride vapour was circulated over the gel for one hour, although 80 minutes were usually sufficient for saturating the gel. It was noticed that the hydrogen chloride content of the gel suffered a slight reduction (about 1.5% of gel by weight) when the gel was saturated with carbon tetrachloride with the aid of the circulation pump.

Selective adsorption studies on hydrogen chloride gel.—Methods of measuring selective adsorption (apparent adsorption) have been described by Jones and Outridge (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 1574), B. S. Rao (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, **36**, 618) and various other workers in the field. The formula used by B. S. Rao is

$$S = m (C_1 - C_2) - 100 \log g.$$

where S denotes selectivity; m , the wt. of the liquid mixture used with the gel; g , wt. of the gel used; C_1 , the initial concentration of the selectively adsorbed liquid and C_2 , the equilibrium concentration of the same liquid. The concentrations are expressed in percentages by weight.

During the removal of water from the gel by the hydrolysis of carbon tetrachloride, samples of the gel had to be heated for 30 hours at 300° and 400°. In order to determine the effect of prolonged heating on selective adsorption, samples of the gel were subjected to the same heat treatment as the hydrogen chloride gel, but without contact with carbon tetrachloride vapour. The selective adsorption of the different samples was measured in the following manner.

The benzene used was the C. P. variety which was dried over phosphorous pentoxide and distilled. The absolute alcohol prepared in the usual manner was finally dried over aluminium amalgam and redistilled. Ten mixtures of varying concentrations were prepared and the refractive indices of these mixtures (found by the Pulfrich

refractometer) were plotted against the concentration of alcohol in the mixture. With the help of this curve the unknown concentration C_2 was determined.

Procedure.—The activated silica gel was introduced into a weighed bottle and was weighed again. The bottle was cooled in ice and the binary mixture added. The bottle was reweighed at the laboratory temperature and kept in a thermostat at 30° for 24 hours. The composition of the equilibrium mixture was determined by refractive index measurement as described above. It was found that the presence of hydrogen chloride does not appreciably affect the refractive index measurements. Alcohol was selectively adsorbed at all concentrations. Tables II and III represent the results.

TABLE II.

Gel 1.		Gel 2.		Gel 3.	
$C_2 \times 100.$	$S \times 100.$	$C_2 \times 100.$	$S \times 100.$	$C_2 \times 100.$	$S \times 100.$
0.2	0.90	0.2	0.73	0.3	0.29
0.3	5.70	0.4	6.35	0.6	7.10
1.3	10.53	2.0	9.72	2.5	9.17
10.1	11.91	12.8	10.95	12.5	10.36
21.3	10.89	23.2	9.98	23.4	9.17
33.5	9.48	34.5	8.55	35.0	7.79
43.8	7.68	45.2	7.04	45.8	6.14
55.3	5.92	57.0	5.20	57.2	4.40
77.3	2.63	78.5	2.41	78.3	1.06
		87.7	1.11	88.2	1.06
		Gel 1.	Gel 2.	Gel 3.	
	$H_2O(\%)$...	2.73	2.43	1.70	
	CCl_4 adsorbed ...	49.63	49.30	47.90	

TABLE III.

Gel 4.		Gel 5.	
$C_2 \times 100.$	$S \times 100.$	$C_2 \times 100.$	$S \times 100.$
0.3	1.05	0.2	0.84
0.6	6.90	0.5	5.58
3.5	7.63	12.0	10.35
12.4	10.90	31.0	12.80
21.7	12.60	41.2	12.40
31.3	12.20	The quantity of the gel was insufficient for more measurements.	
53.5	7.85		
77.0	4.31		
88.0	2.42		
	HCl content. ...	11.68	8.5%
	CCl_4 adsorption ...	42.73	43.20%

The selectivity-concentration curves given in Fig. 2, indicate change in selectivity caused by prolonged activation and by replacement of water by hydrogen chloride.

FIG. 2.

Curves 1-4 represent $S-C_2$ curve for gel no. 4, 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

DISCUSSION.

From Fig. 2, it is clear that when the gel is heated for 30 hours at 300° and 400° , the selectivity decreases. Hence prolonged heating seems to have a deleterious effect on the surface of the gel causing a diminution in the selective adsorption, though the internal volume of the capillaries in the gel is not appreciably affected. If the gel is ignited in a platinum dish for one hour, the total adsorption of carbon tetrachloride is reduced to 6.5% while the selective adsorption at its maximum is hardly 0.005. Hydrogen chloride gel takes up less liquid (indicating reduction in capillary space) but the selectivity of the gel is appreciably enhanced.

SUMMARY.

1. Adsorptive properties of silica gel in which residual water has been replaced by hydrogen chloride have been compared with those of ordinary gel.
2. The effect on selective adsorption caused by the prolonged heating of silica gel during activation has been studied.

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